

Assessment of Health Risk Factors Associated with Flood Disaster in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the health risk factors associated with flood disaster in the Niger Delta of Nigeria, using the cross-sectional survey research design and 400 copies of questionnaire to elicit information in the selected communities on the health risk factors and the public health intervention to prevent non-communicable and communicable diseases. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis. The results showed that communities sampled are aware of risk factors influencing health problems which include the speed of the flood water, depth of the flood, collapse of houses and destruction of infrastructure that are associated with physical health problem. Risk factors such as overcrowding in camp, disruption of sewage disposal, negligible sanitation and stagnant water, poor standard of hygiene, poor nutrition are associated with both the vector and water-borne diseases. Also, the loss of loved once, destruction of houses, source of income, and farmland constitute the risk factors associated with mental health problem. Among the common intervention practices adopted include clearing of drainage system, establishing hubs for treatment and care after flood disaster, continuous visitation by health professional, immunization program, clearing of drains, provision of health services and WASH within the communities. The study concluded that flooding plays important role in the physical and mental health, outbreak and the spread of infectious diseases as it creates conditions for injuries and the multiplication of pathogens and vectors. It recommends that policymakers should invest more in strategies that would improve risk perception, enhance awareness, while providing functional local health care system and assistance to communities over a longer period.

Keywords: *Risk factors, flood, health risk, disaster, accessibility, hazard assessment.*

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Introduction

Natural disasters often cause disorders in the ecosystem and pose multiple dangers to human and animal health (Cousins, 2017 & Okaka &

Odhiambo, 2018). Floods are the most common and widespread geo-environmental disasters all around the world (Bich Quang, Thanh Ha, Duc Hanh, & Guha-Sapir, 2011; Paterson Wright, &

Harris, 2018). Floods for several reasons lead to mortality and morbidity (Brown and Murray, 2013; Alderman et al., 2012; Shokri, Sabzevari, & Hashemi, 2020) and as one of the major environmental challenges, have been caused by many factors. Heavy rains, river and coastal floods, and human interferences (e.g. deforestation, urbanization, poor urban drainage) are examples of flooding causes (Okaka & Odhiambo, 2018). In the twenty-first century, flood hazard due to climate change and global warming has attracted significant concern and international attention (Okaka & Odhiambo, 2018; Paterson *et al.*, 2018; Lin *et al.*, 2015).

Infectious disease is a major health concern following flood in settings, where infectious disease transmission is an endemic public health problem. According to Watson et al. (2007), Infectious disease outbreaks have been reported following major flood events in developing countries, and these outbreaks vary in magnitude and rates of mortality (Ahmed *et al.*, 2011). Onset of flood results in an even higher infectious diseases burden, both in absolute and relative term. Flooding is associated with an increased risk of infection; risk factors that would include are population displacement, inadequate shelter conditions, degree of overcrowding, drinking contaminated water, improper sanitation, an underlying health status of population, malnutrition, local diseases ecology and difficulties in accessibility of health care services (Ahmed, Akerib, Arrenberg, Bailey, Balakishiyeva, Baudis, & CDMS Collaboration, 2011). Provision of relief must consider the situation of infectious diseases in areas where flood has potential risk to human (Kondo, et al., 2002; Ahmed *et al.*, 2011).

In the last two decades, over 5000 water-related disasters (WRDs) occurred globally, accounting for 73.9% of all-natural disasters. In total, WRDs (i.e., floods, storms, landslides, and droughts) caused over 300,000 fatalities and ~ 1.7 trillion USD in economic damages worldwide (Lee *et al.*, 2020). Floods and droughts, which account for nearly 60% of WRDs, have especially had significant economic repercussions in recent history. In the 20th century, an estimated 365 billion USD was lost worldwide due to

approximately 2100 floods and 430 droughts (Lee *et al.*, 2020). The 21st century thus far has experienced a higher frequency of WRDs and their associated consequences: from 2001 to 2018, about 600 billion USD was lost globally due to over 2900 flood or 290 drought events. These events have also had disastrous health impacts on 2.8 billion people. For instance, nearly 300,000 people suffered from flood-related physical injuries during 2001–2018 (Lee, Perera, Glickman & Taing., 2020).

Flood impact the human community either directly through contact with the water or indirectly through the damage the water does to the natural and human-built environment. Even relatively small, localized floods may have a significant impact on people's physical and mental health. One study found a four-fold increase in illnesses among people whose homes had been flooded compared with those whose homes were not flooded. Not only is the incidence of floods increasing, but also rapid urbanization is resulting in the exposure of more people to floods. In addition, it is projected that global warming will have an impact on the frequency of floods worldwide. Management of the health impacts of floods is dependent upon an extensive knowledge and understanding of the health risks and on the capacity of the health system to mitigate or manage those consequences (Lowe, et al 2013). All floods are unique in that the regions affected have different social, demographic, economic, and population health characteristics. Yet, many similarities exist, and knowledge of the causes of death and types of injuries and illnesses from floods is essential to help to ensure that health and emergency medical relief is well-managed. Based on this, the present study intends to assess the health risk factors associated with flood-affected communities in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria as well as determine the public health intervention to prevent the deterioration of non-communicable and communicable diseases in the study area.

Literature Review

Concept of Flood Risk and Hazard Assessment

Flood risk is a combination of the probability (likelihood or chance) of an event happening and the consequences (impact) if it occurred. Flood risk is dependent on there being a source of flooding, such as a river, a route for the flood water to take (pathway), and something that is affected by the flood (receptor), such as a housing estate (van Western, 2013). Without a pathway linking the source to the receptor, a flood may be a hazard, but not a risk. This concept is known as the *Source-Pathway-Receptor Model*. The likelihood of a flooding event happening can often be misleading or confusing. Return periods are often used to describe how often a flooding event will occur, but using terms such as 1 in 50 years or 1 in 500 years can mislead the public into thinking that a 1 in 50 year flood

event will only occur every 50 years. Return periods are an average of how often a flood event of that magnitude will occur, and so the probability or chance of flooding should be used instead, so for example, a 1 in 50 year flood has a 2 per cent probability of occurring in any one year.

The consequences of a flood depend on two factors, exposure and vulnerability. Exposure is a measure of the number of people or things that may be affected by a flood while vulnerability is a measure of the potential of people or things to be harmed. For example, the consequences of a flood will be less severe in an area with very few people (low exposure) who are able to evacuate quickly and easily (low vulnerability). Flooding in an area with lots of people (high exposure) who have difficulty with evacuation (high vulnerability) is likely to have more serious consequences (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flood Risk Components

Source: van Western (2013)

Hazard refers to the possible, future occurrence of natural or human-induced physical events that may have adverse effects on vulnerable and exposed elements (Birkmann, 2006; Cardona *et al.*, 2012). Although, at times, hazard has been ascribed the same meaning as risk, currently it is widely accepted that it is a component of risk and not risk itself. The intensity or recurrence of hazard events can be partly determined by environmental degradation and human intervention in natural ecosystems. Landslides or

flooding regimes associated with human-induced environmental alteration and new climate change-related hazards are examples of such socio-natural hazards (Lavell, 1996, Cardona *et al.*, 2012).

Flood hazard assessment and mapping is used to identify areas at risk of flooding, and consequently to improve flood risk management and disaster preparedness. Flood hazard assessments and maps typically look at the expected extent and depth of flooding in a given

location, based on various scenarios (e.g. 100-year events, 50-year events, etc.) (UN-Water & Environment, 2016). Measures to improve preparedness can include changes in land-use planning, implementation of specific flood-proofing measures, creation of emergency response plans, etc. Flood hazard assessments can be further expanded to assess specific risks, which take into consideration the socioeconomic characteristics (e.g. industrial activities, population density, land use) of the exposed areas (UN-Water & Environment, 2016).

Risk Exposure Theory (Terje Aven, 2012)

Disaster risk signifies the possibility of adverse effects in the future. It derives from the interaction of social and environmental processes, from the combination of physical hazards and the vulnerabilities of exposed elements. The hazard event is not the sole driver of risk, and there is *high confidence* that the levels of adverse effects are in good part determined by the vulnerability and exposure of societies and social-ecological systems (UNISDR, 2009; Birkmann, 2006). Disaster risk is associated with differing levels and types of adverse effects. The effects may assume catastrophic levels or levels commensurate with small disasters. Some have limited financial costs but very high human costs in terms of loss of life and numbers of people affected; others have very high financial costs but relatively limited human costs. Furthermore, there is *high confidence* that the cumulative effects of small disasters can affect capacities of communities, societies, or social ecological systems to deal with future disasters at sub-national or local levels (Birkmann, 2006).

Empirical Review

Using time series study, Yang *et al.* (2023) evaluate lag-response associations and effect modifications of exposure to floods with risks of all cause, cardiovascular, and respiratory mortality on a global scale. The study involved 761 communities in 35 countries or territories with at least one flood event during the study period. A total of 47.6 million all cause deaths, 11.1 million cardiovascular deaths, and 4.9 million respiratory deaths were analysed. Over the 761 communities, mortality risks increased

and persisted for up to 60 days (50 days for cardiovascular mortality) after a flooded day. The cumulative relative risks for all cause, cardiovascular, and respiratory mortality were 1.021 (95% confidence interval 1.006 to 1.036), 1.026 (1.005 to 1.047), and 1.049 (1.008 to 1.092), respectively. The associations varied across countries or territories and regions. The flood-mortality associations appeared to be modified by climate type and were stronger in low income countries and in populations with a low human development index or high proportion of older people. In communities impacted by flood, up to 0.10% of all cause deaths, 0.18% of cardiovascular deaths, and 0.41% of respiratory deaths were attributed to floods. This study found that the risks of all cause, cardiovascular, and respiratory mortality increased for up to 60 days after exposure to flood and the associations could vary by local climate type, socioeconomic status, and older age.

Shah *et al.* (2020) investigates households' vulnerability to public health risks in disaster-prone areas of Pakistan. It uses a dataset of 600 households, based on structured questionnaire with household heads from two severely flood-affected districts (Nowshera and Charsadda) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP). Household vulnerability to flooding and related health problems are assessed through a logistic regression model. The results reveal that respondents' socio-economic and demographic attributes, such as age, gender, education, income, the materials out of which their house is constructed, past experience of floods and social networks are the key factors influencing their flood vulnerability. Households' health vulnerability is affected by their access to information and health facilities, their sanitary arrangements, distance from the main health facility and previous damage to water supply and health facilities from the flood in 2010. The findings suggest the need to overcome households' flood and health vulnerability through capacity building, training and sustainable mitigation efforts. At the governmental level, a comprehensive and realistic stakeholder analysis is needed to ensure the active involvement of all stakeholders, to

generate their commitment and support and to identify what actions are most needed. Any actions to minimize household health risks will require an integrated, multi-sector, approach which would increase efficiency through pooling resources and skills.

Shokri *et al.* (2020) reviewed the impacts of flood on health of Iranian population: infectious diseases with an emphasis on parasitic infections. A comprehensive search was carried out in databases including PubMed, Google scholar, Scopus, Science Direct, Iran medex, Magiran and SID (Scientific information database) from 2000 to 2019. All original descriptive articles on flood were concerned. Related articles on flood disturbance were considered. Also, publication of red cross society was considered as only reliable reference in evaluation of consequences of flood occurred in 2019 in Iran. Flooding in Iran, was started in March 2019 and lasted to April 2019. Flood affected 31 provinces and 140 rivers burst their banks, and southwestern Iran being hit most severely. According the reports of international federation of red cross society, 3800 cities and villages were affected by the floods with 65,000 destroyed houses and 114,000 houses partially damaged. Also 70 hospitals or health care centers with 1200 schools were damaged along with many infrastructures including 159 main roads and 700 bridges. Considering 365,000 displaced persons and estimation of mentioned damages, it was one of the greatest natural disaster during the last 20 years.

Various risk factors in favour of infectious diseases such as overcrowding, disruption of sewage disposal, poor standards of hygiene, poor nutrition, negligible sanitation and human contact among refugees provide suitable conditions for increased incidence of infectious diseases after flooding and also cause epidemics. More attention is needed to provide hygienic situation for people after natural disasters including flood. Olanrewaju *et al.*, (2019) critically evaluated the health implications and flood disaster management in Nigeria using quantitative and qualitative data sources. The study revealed poorly managed health reforms and argues that in spite of government's disaster management policies, there is an absence of

organized and coordinated institutional structures to plan and respond to flood emergencies. It also revealed that diarrhoea outbreak was the predominant waterborne disease associated with flood disasters. Although Lagos State has been said to have the best flood preparedness plan in Nigeria, it has failed to reduce the yearly flood disasters and their impact on the health of the people. Therefore, suggested a holistic approach by the government to get stakeholders, especially the health sector, more actively involved in disaster management planning.

Materials and Methods

The study employed the cross-sectional survey research design. The cross sectional research design gives clarity of the work, detailed and definite explanation concerning the situation and aspects under examination. The population of the study was limited to 3 selected states in Niger Delta Region which includes Rivers, Bayelsa and Delta Sate, which stood at 2,425,745. With the aid of Taro Yamane formula, a sample size of 400 was determined and out of this number, 363 copies of the questionnaire administered were properly filled and retrieved. The questionnaire instrument was administered on persons chosen by the inclusive criteria of study i.e. their knowledge of flooding, health care management amidst flood disaster, situation of the past and present flooding and general knowledge about health risks. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for data presentation and analysis. The research hypotheses of the study were tested through inferential statistics (Analysis of Variance-ANOVA) at a 95% significance level.

Study Area

The study area is the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The Niger Delta Region of Nigeria is located at 4°49'60" N and 6°0'00" East as shown in (Figure 2). It protrudes towards the Gulf of Guinea on the Atlantic coast of West Africa (Shittu, 2014). The region is a densely populated area in Nigeria. Its population is about 31 million people. The land mass extends about 70,000 km², making up 7.5% of Nigeria's landmass.

Figure 2. The Niger Delta Region States
Source: State Boundary from Open Street Map (2018)

Results and Discussions

The result was carried out in line with the objectives which the study was set to achieve. The result is presented as follows:

Health Risk Factors Associated with Flood Disaster in the Selected Communities

The health risk factors associated with flood disasters were examined among the communities in the Niger Delta region, and the outcome was presented in Table 1. Considering the risk factors influencing community health problems, 97.2% of the respondents indicated they were aware of the risk factors, while 2.8% indicated they were not. On risk factors associated with a physical health problem, 24.8% of the respondents indicated that the speed of the flood water is the risk factor associated with a physical health problem, 32.0% of the respondents suggested the depth of the flood while 35.8% and 4.7% of the respondents indicated the collapse of houses and destruction of electrical infrastructure are the risk factor

associated with physical health problem respectively. The outcome deduced that overcrowding in camps (16.5%), disruption of sewage disposal (17.4%), negligible sanitation (11.8%) and long-standing water (54.0%) are the risk factors associated with vector-borne diseases. From the outcome, it was deduced that poor standard of hygiene (39.4%), poor nutrition (57.3%), disruption of sewage disposal (1.9%) and negligible sanitation (1.4%) are the risk factors associated with water-borne diseases. Among the respondents, it was deduced that loss of loved ones (22.0%), destruction of the house (17.4%), destruction of the source of income (39.7%) and destruction of farmland (20.4%) are the risk factors associated with a mental health problems. Considering the factors related to the malnutrition problem, 51.0% of the respondents indicated a lack of good food, 42.7% indicated poor nutrition, and 6.3% indicated negligible sanitation is the risk factor associated with the malnutrition problem.

Table 1. Health Risk Factors Associated with Flood Disaster

Variables	Rivers		Bayelsa		Delta		Total (%)
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Aware of Risk Factors Influencing Health Problems							
Yes, I am Aware	95	99.0	160	97.0	98	96.1	353 (97.2)
No, I am not Aware	1	1.0	5	3.0	4	3.9	10 (2.8)
							363 (100)
Risk factors associated with physical health problems							
Speed of the Floodwater	24	25.0	48	29.1	18	17.6	90 (24.8)
Depth of the Flood	20	20.8	44	26.7	52	51.0	116 (32.0)
Collapse of Houses	43	44.8	59	35.8	28	27.5	130 (35.8)
Destruction of Electrical Infrastructure	8	8.3	6	3.6	3	2.9	17 (4.7)
Others	1	1.0	8	4.8	1	1.0	10 (2.8)
							363 (100)
Risk factors associated with Vector-borne Disease							
Overcrowding in Camp	23	24.0	24	14.5	13	12.7	60 (16.5)
Disruption of Sewage Disposal	23	24.0	26	15.8	14	13.7	63 (17.4)
Negligible Sanitation	6	6.3	26	15.8	11	10.8	43 (11.8)
Long-Standing Water	44	45.8	89	53.9	63	61.8	196 (54.0)
Others					1	1.0	1 (0.3)
							363 (100)
Risk factors associated with Water-borne Diseases							
Poor Standard of Hygiene	37	38.5	42	25.5	64	62.7	143 (39.4)
Poor Nutrition	56	58.3	118	71.5	34	33.3	208 (57.3)
Disruption of Sewage Disposal	-	-	4	2.4	3	2.9	7 (1.9)
Negligible Sanitation	3	3.1	1	.6	1	1.0	5 (1.4)
							363 (100)
Risk factors associated with Mental Health Disease							
Loss of Loved Once	44	45.8	25	15.2	11	10.8	80 (22.0)
Destruction of Houses	23	24.0	30	18.2	10	9.8	63 (17.4)
Destruction of Source of Income	15	15.6	63	38.2	66	64.7	144 (39.7)
Destruction of Farmland	14	14.6	47	28.5	13	12.7	74 (20.4)
Others					2	2.0	2 (0.6)
							363 (100)
Risk factors associated with Malnutrition Problem							
Lack of good food	31	32.3	89	53.9	65	63.7	185 (51.0)
Poor nutrition	58	60.4	62	37.6	35	34.3	155 (42.7)
Negligible Sanitation	7	7.3	14	8.5	2	2.0	23 (6.3)
							363 (100)

Note: *n = Frequency, % = Percentage

Source: Researcher’s fieldwork, 2024

Hypothesis I

From Table 2, the study's hypothesis was tested using the ANOVA. The hypothesis was tested based on the following statement:

H₀: There is no significant difference in the health risk factors associated with flood disasters among the selected communities of the study area

In explaining the outcome of the significance tests, the p-value was adopted to determine the significance levels (where $p \leq 0.05$ rejects the null hypothesis). Based on the outcome, the analysis showed a significant difference in the health risk factors (for vector- and water-borne, mental health and malnutrition problems) associated with flood disasters among the selected communities (where $p \leq 0.05$, $p = 0.007$, 0.000 , 0.000 and 0.000 respectively).

However, the analysis deduced that there was no significant difference in the health risk factors (for physical health problems) associated with

flood disasters among the selected communities (where $p \leq 0.05$, $p = 0.333$).

Table 2. Significant Different Analysis of Risk Factors Associated with Flood Disaster

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Risk factors associated with physical health problems	Between Groups	2.279	2	1.139	1.103	0.333
	Within Groups	368.821	357	1.033		
	Total	371.100	359			
Risk factors associated with Vector-Borne Disease	Between Groups	13.796	2	6.898	5.032	0.007
	Within Groups	493.498	360	1.371		
	Total	507.295	362			
Risk factors associated with Water-Borne Disease	Between Groups	7.360	2	3.680	10.015	0.000
	Within Groups	132.282	360	.367		
	Total	139.642	362			
Risk Factors Associated with Mental Health Problems	Between Groups	49.934	2	24.967	24.376	0.000
	Within Groups	368.733	360	1.024		
	Total	418.667	362			
Risk factors associated with Malnutrition problem	Between Groups	6.187	2	3.093	8.715	0.000
	Within Groups	127.418	359	.355		
	Total	133.605	361			

Source: Researcher's fieldwork, 2024

The finding revealed that communities are aware of risk factors influencing health problem in the communities. The findings further revealed that factors such as speed of the flood water, depth of the flood, collapse of houses and destruction of infrastructure are associated with physical health problem. Risk factors such as overcrowding in camp, disruption of sewage disposal, negligible sanitation and long-standing water are associated with vector-borne diseases. Risk factors such as poor standard of hygiene, poor nutrition, disruption of sewage disposal and negligible sanitation are associated with water-borne diseases. The outcome of the study revealed that loss of loved once, destruction of house, destruction of source of income and destruction of farmland are the risk factors associated with mental health problem. Regarding malnutrition due to flood disaster, the finding revealed that lack of good food, poor nutrition and negligible sanitation are the risk factors associated with malnutrition problem. The finding share similarity with the study of Paterson *et al.* (2018) which identified similar risk factors associated with flood waters. Paterson *et al.* (2018) further suggested that risk of death is

dependent on the speed of onset of flooding and this assertion was similar to the present study which identified speed of the flood water as a major risk factor leading to physical injuries and drowning.

Considering the differences in the risk factors associated with health problem among communities, it was revealed that collapse of building was the major factor for communities in Rivers and Bayelsa State while depth of the flood was the leading factor among communities in Delta State. Across the studied communities, the common risk factor associated with vector-borne diseases is the long standing of water in the environment.

Public Health Intervention to Prevent Non-Communicable and Communicable Diseases

The public health intervention to prevent non-communicable and communicable disease among the communities in the Niger Delta region was examined and the outcome was presented in Table 3. From the analysis, 48.5% of the respondents revealed to be aware of

public health intervention for non-communicable diseases while 51.5% of the respondents revealed not to be aware of public health intervention for non-communicable diseases. Similarly, 47.4% of the respondents revealed to be aware of public health intervention for communicable diseases while 52.6% of the respondents revealed not to be aware of public health intervention for communicable diseases. On the public health intervention for non-communicable diseases, 19.0% of the respondents indicated clearing of drainage system, 25.3% of the respondents indicated establishing hubs for treatment and care after flood disaster, 18.7% indicated continuous visitation by health professionals while 11.3% and 8.8% of the respondents indicated pre-planning with pharmaceutical and medical equipment suppliers and rebuild

healthcare infrastructure to new location respectively. The finding revealed that the public health intervention for non-communicable diseases was not effective (39.7%) and less effective (39.1%) among the communities in the study area. On the public health intervention for communicable diseases, 35.0% of the respondents indicated immunization program, 24.8% of the respondent's indicated removal or destruction of all solid debris, 14.0% indicated health services while 12.4% and 8.5% of the respondents indicated provision of water, sanitation and proper site planning and sensitization on healthy practices respectively. The finding revealed that the public health intervention for communicable diseases was not effective (38.8%) and less effective (36.1%) among the communities in the study area.

Table 3. Post-Flood Public Health Intervention Practices in the Community

Variables	Rivers		Bayelsa		Delta		Total (%)
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Aware of Public Health Intervention for Non-Communicable							
Yes, I am Aware	46	47.9	114	69.1	16	15.7	176 (48.5)
No, I am not Aware	50	52.1	51	30.9	86	84.3	187 (51.5)
							363 (100)
Aware of Public Health Intervention for Communicable Disease							
Yes, I am Aware	43	44.8	112	67.9	15	14.7	172 (47.4)
No, I am not Aware	53	55.2	53	32.1	87	85.3	191 (52.6)
Public Health Intervention for Non-Communicable Disease							
Health professional continuously visiting camp	39	40.6	14	8.5	15	14.7	68 (18.7)
Rebuild healthcare infrastructure to new location	14	14.5	12	7.3	6	5.9	32 (8.8)
Establish Hubs for Treatment and Care after Flood Disaster	7	7.3	80	48.5	5	4.9	92 (25.3)
Preplanning with Pharmaceutical and Medical Equipment Suppliers	6	6.3	27	16.3	8	7.8	41 (11.3)
Clearing all Drainage System	24	25.0	30	18.2	15	14.7	69 (19.0)
Others	6	6.3	2	1.2	53	52.0	61 (16.8)
							363 (100)
Effectiveness of Public Health Intervention for Non-Communicable Disease							
Not Effective	12	12.5	58	35.2	74	72.5	144 (39.7)
Less Effective	70	72.9	57	34.5	15	14.7	142 (39.1)
Effective	10	10.4	49	29.7	13	12.7	72 (19.8)
Very Effective	4	4.2	1	.6			5 (1.4)
							363 (100)
Public Health Intervention for Communicable Disease							
Provision of Safe Water, Sanitation and Proper Site Planning	22	22.9	11	6.7	12	11.8	45 (12.4)

Ensure Healthcare Services	19	19.8	22	13.3	10	9.8	51 (14.0)
Immunization Program	15	15.6	103	62.4	9	8.8	127 (35.0)
Sensitization on Healthy Practices	16	16.7	13	7.9	2	2.0	31 (8.5)
Removal or Destruction of all Solid Debris	22	22.9	3	1.8	65	63.7	90 (24.8)
Others	2	2.1	13	7.9	4	3.9	19 (5.2)
							363 (100)
Effectiveness of Public Health Intervention for Communicable Disease							
Not Effective	12	12.5	57	34.5	72	70.6	141 (38.8)
Less Effective	67	69.8	50	30.3	14	13.7	131 (36.1)
Effective	15	15.6	53	32.1	16	15.7	84 (23.1)
Very Effective	2	2.1	5	3.1			7 (2.0)
							363 (100)

Note: *n = Frequency, % = Percentage

Source: Researcher's fieldwork, 2024

Hypothesis II

From Table 4, the study's hypothesis was tested using the ANOVA. The hypothesis was tested based on the following statement:

H₀: There is no significant difference in the public health intervention to prevent deterioration of non-communicable and communicable disease in the study area.

In explaining the outcome from the significance tests, the p-value was adopted to determine the levels of significance (where $p \leq 0.05$ rejects the null hypothesis). Based on the outcome, the analysis showed a significant difference in the public health intervention to prevent deterioration of non-communicable and communicable disease in the study area (where $p \leq 0.05$, $p = 0.000$ and 0.000 for non-communicable and communicable disease respectively).

Table 4. Significant Different Analysis of Public health intervention practices

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Public health intervention practice for non-communicable disease					
Between Groups	189.930	2	94.965	33.338	0.000
Within Groups	951.411	334	2.849		
Total	1141.341	336			
Public health intervention practice for Communicable disease					
Between Groups	203.176	2	101.588	47.067	0.000
Within Groups	766.224	355	2.158		
Total	969.399	357			

Source: Researcher's fieldwork, 2024

The respondents indicated not to be aware of the public health intervention to prevent non-communicable and communicable disease among the communities; however, the percentage of those that indicated to be aware was sufficient for further questions regarding the various intervention practices available for non-communicable and communicable disease in their communities. In this regard, it was deduced

that the most common intervention practices available for non-communicable was clearing of drainage system, establish hubs for treatment and care after flood disaster and continuous visitation by health professional. Also, it was deduced that the most common intervention practices available for communicable was immunization program, removal or destruction of all solid debris and provision of health

services and WASH among the communities. The findings share similarity with the study conducted by Amangabara and Obenade (2015) which identified routine vaccination programmes as part of intervention program for flood victim. The finding deduced that public health intervention practices for non-communicable and communicable disease among the communities are not effective. The is outcome is corroborated with that of Amangabara and Obenade (2015) which asserted that various health services program for Niger Delta States are either short supply or inefficiently managed. The outcome share similarity with the study conducted by Shokri *et al.* (2020) and Lowe, et al (2013) which suggested mass immunization along with vitamin A supplements couple with removal or destruction of solid debris are critical to prevention programs.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study strongly suggested that the speed of the flood water, overcrowding in camps, poor standard of hygiene, loss of loved ones, and lack of good food as the health risk factors associated with physical health problems, vector and water-borne diseases, mental health problem and malnutrition during and after the flood disaster. Therefore, the study concluded that flooding plays an important role in the physical and mental health, outbreak and the spread of infectious diseases as it creates conditions for injuries and the multiplication of pathogens and vectors.

Based on the outcome of the study, it was recommended that there is need for policymakers to invest in communication strategies to increase the risk perception of the population as higher perceived risk is strongly correlated with the likelihood of taking preventive measures. Also, relief organizations and government efforts need to develop a local health care system, which will remain on ground and give assistance to communities over a longer period.

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